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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Ms. Aparna Jain, Research Scholar & Dr.Pramod Gupta (2017), “An Analytical Study Of Sustainable Human Resource Policies And Talent Management In Indian Scenario”, *International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management*, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue7, Jul-2017), pp 14-25, DOI URL:

AN ANALYTICAL STUDY OF SUSTAINABLE HUMAN RESOURCE POLICIES AND TALENT MANAGEMENT IN INDIAN SCENARIO

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ABSTRACT

In a recent survey of Indian CEO's, it was suggested that Indian managerial leaders were less dependent on their personal charisma, but they emphasised logical and step by step implementation processes. Indian leaders focused on empowerment and accountability in cases of critical turnaround challenges, innovative challenges, innovative technology, product planning and marketing or when other similar challenges were encountered (Spencer, Rajah, Narayan, Mohan & Latiri 2007). These social scientists contend.

Leaders in other countries often tell about why they chose a peculiar person for a certain role per task, detailing the personal characteristics that made that person right for that situation. They may also consider, in detail, how an assignment would help someone grow and develop their abilities. In general, Indian leaders simply did not discuss how they matched particular people to certain roles or tasks, nor did they usually consider in detail how the personal characteristics of individuals might shape or inform the best way to influence that person. (Spencer, et al 2007:90).

Key-Words: Sustainability, Human Resource Management, sustainable enterprises, TAP, PEP,

ACT.

Introduction:

The role of HRM in developing sustainable business organizations is increasingly attracting attention. Sustainability can be used as a principle for HRM itself and the tasks of Sustainable HRM are twofold. On the one hand it fosters the conditions for individual employee sustainability and develops the ability of HRM systems to continuously attract, regenerate and develop motivated and engaged employees by making the HRM system itself sustainable. On the other hand Sustainable HRM contributes to the sustainability of the business organizations through cooperation with the top management, key stakeholders and NGOs and by realising economic, ecological, social and human sustainability goals. This book provides a comprehensive review of the new area of Sustainable HRM and of research from different disciplines like sustainable work systems, ergonomics, HRM, linking sustainability and HRM. It brings together the views of academics and practitioners and provides many ideas for conceptual development, empirical exploration and practical implementation. This publication intends to advance the international academic and practice-based debates on the potential of sustainability for HRM and vice versa.

Thus the domain of talent management focuses not only on development of individual's intrinsic capacities, but also on culture building and change management to provide the other elements listed above for manifestation of talent into performance. The service and consulting areas of talent management that thus emerge are:

- Talent appreciation
- Potential enhancement
- Acquisition of talent
- Knowledge Management.

Grow Talent offers services in all the above areas. Grow Talent’s offerings are based on the models discussed above and follow a unique methodology.

Talent appreciation: - (TAP)

TAP services from Grow Talent are focused on assessing the way individuals learn, think, relate to others, and act. Tap is used to evaluate the capacities, competencies and values of individuals for assessment of potential for career development and succession planning. This is intricately linked to helping organizations map their capacity and competency requirements and then assessing talent to draw up individual development plans. The talent profiling thus done for organizations helps them identify critical competencies to be developed and capacities to be enhanced in order to meet future business requirements and achieve plans.

Potential enhancement: - (PEP)

The focus of PEP is to create learning experiences and solutions for individuals that will help convert their talent into competence. It also involves designing learning events and processes that enhance the potential of individuals. Two intrinsic components of Grow Talent PEP are:

- ❖ Capacity building modules - which focus on enhancing the four capacities of individuals
- ❖ Competence building modules – which focus on specific areas like consulting skills, problem solving, and service quality, strategic selling, process designing, interviewing skills, etc.

Acquisition of talent: - (ACT)

Grow Talent’s approach to helping organizations acquire talent is based on the following:

- Helping organizations define roles for specific leadership positions based on preferred futures' and strategy.
- Identifying the competencies required for each of these jobs.
- Determining the levels of fundamental capacities of learning, thinking, relating and acting needed to acquire these competencies.
- Defining the values which are needed to display the desired behaviors.
- Identifying individuals who would fit into these positions.

Enable organizations and individuals to establish mutually acceptable contracts for employment and lay the foundation of win-win relationships.

Knowledge Management:

As said earlier, the domain of talent management includes culture-building and change management. Knowledge management services from Grow Talent are aimed at leveraging knowledge for performance by creating an environment for sharing by building trust. The focus of knowledge management is to connect people and technology to capture and harness the tacit knowledge of the organization. By making trust the bandwidth of communication, knowledge management enhances sharing and thereby creates an appropriate environment for talent to translate into performance. With its comprehensive spectrum of services for talent management and unique methodology, Grow Talent is strongly positioned to help organizations gain a competitive and sustained talent advantage.

Objectives of the Research Work:

1. To identify various upcoming challenges of talent management
2. To establish upcoming trends in talent management.
3. To study the various HRD practices and its components like Recruitment and Selection, Training and Development practices career development initiatives and performance Appraisal system adapted to Manage talent by the Organizations in Indian Industries.
4. To study the process and components of Talent management like acquisition, maintenance and retention of talent in Indian industries.

Research Methodology & Data Analysis:

For the present study both exploratory and conclusive research methods were used. The conclusive research method here is descriptive in nature and the research design is single cross sectional. In this study primary data has been collected through questionnaire method. The research was conducted with the help of a questionnaire measuring the job values, managerial style, effective personal management and human resources practices of 15 IT companies situated in Delhi and NCR region. The chosen research design mainly emphasizes on the discovery of ideas and development of insight into the subjects under study.

The data in exploratory and conclusive research methods are obtained largely through interview and questionnaire techniques where direct observation techniques and employees perception for the several issues of HRD behavior were applied. The data used in this study satisfies following conditions:

1. Log of several news papers, magazine related to corporate citizenship behavior of employees in organizations.
2. To validate the log data, some respondents were selected and relevant information and data was collected by them.
3. Question asked to respondents were related to job values, personal management, human resource practices and managerial effectiveness. Responses were collected through a structured questionnaire separately designed for viewers or the respondents.

Analysis and Presentation:-

The data obtained through questionnaire were analyzed by using appropriate statistical tools. The filled up questionnaires were coded and master data sheet was prepared. The data was then tabulated and classified. The statistical tests which were applied are as follows:

Cronbach’s Alpha: Reliability comes to the forefront when variables developed from summated scales are used as predictor components in objective models. Since summated scales are an assembly of interrelated items designed to measure underlying constructs, it is very important to know whether the same set of items would elicit the same responses if the same questions are recast and re-administered to the same respondents. Cronbach’s alpha is an index of reliability associated with the variation accounted for by the true score of the “underlying construct.” Construct is the hypothetical variable that is being measured (Hatcher, 1994). Alpha coefficient ranges in value from 0 to 1 and may be used to describe the reliability of factors extracted from dichotomous (that is, questions with two possible answers) and/or multi-point formatted questionnaires or scales (i.e., rating scale: 1 = poor, 5 = excellent). The higher the score, the more reliable the generated scale is.

One-Way ANOVA: In statistics, one-way analysis of variance (abbreviated one-way ANOVA) is a technique used to compare means of two or more samples (using the F-distribution). This technique can be used only for numerical data. The ANOVA tests the null hypothesis that samples in two or more groups are drawn from populations with the same mean values. Typically, however, the one-way ANOVA is used to test for differences among at least three groups, since the two-group case can be covered by a t-test (Gosset, 1908). The results of a one-way ANOVA can be considered reliable as long as the following assumptions are met:

- Response variable are normally distributed (or approximately normally distributed).
- Samples are independent.
- Variances of populations are equal.
- Responses for a given group are independent and identically distributed normal random variables (not a simple random sample (SRS)).

ANOVA is a relatively robust procedure with respect to violations of the normality assumption. If data are ordinal, a non-parametric alternative to this test should be used such as Kruskal-Wallis one-way analysis of variance.

2-Way ANOVA: In statistics, the two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test is an extension of the one-way ANOVA test that examines the influence of different categorical independent variables on one dependent variable. The two-way ANOVA can not only determine the main effect of contributions of each independent variable but also identifies if there is a significant interaction effect between the independent variables. As with other parametric tests, we make the following assumptions when using two-way ANOVA:

- The populations from which the samples are obtained must be normally distributed.
- Sampling is done correctly. Observations for within and between groups must be independent.
- The variances among populations must be equal (homoscedastic).
- Data are interval or nominal.

HRD STATISTICS IN TALENT MANAGEMENT PROCESS;

Frequencies

Total 15 IT companies are under study. Their number of respondent employees, frequencies of their responses is shown in Table 1.1 with variable statistic values.

Table 1.1

HRD Statistics

		Respondent Companies	More than 1000 employees	More than 500 employees	Less than 500 employees
	Valid	15	5	5	5
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean			22.50	22.00	22.80
Std. Error of Mean			.500	.558	.490
Median			22.00	22.00	22.00
Mode			22	22 ^(a)	22
Std. Deviation			.894	1.225	1.095
Variance			.800	1.500	1.200
Skewness			2.236	-1.361	.609
Std. Error of Skewness			.913	.913	.913
Percentiles	25		22.00	21.00	22.00
	50		22.00	22.00	22.00
	75		23.00	23.00	24.00

^(a) Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown. Source: Primary Data, Author's Compilation

As can be seen from Table 1.1, total 15 IT companies have been chosen. Three groups having 5 companies each have been made according to numbers of respondents with more than 1000, more than 500 and less than 500 of a group respectively. There is not any significant difference between mean values of different respondent groups which are 22.50, 22.00 and 22.80 respectively. Median and mode values are equal for all groups. Standard deviation was highest (1.225) for group having more than 500 respondents (let G₂), followed by (1.095) for group having less than 500 respondents (let G₃) whereas lowest (0.894) for the group having more than 1000 respondents (let G₁).

Variance value was 1.500 (highest) for G₂, followed by 1.200 for G₃ and lowest 0.800 for the respondent group G₁. On the other hand, skewness value was 2.236 (highest) for G₁ followed

by 0.609 for G_3 and lowest with negative value -1.361 for G_2 although standard error was same for each group.

Frequency Table of Respondent Companies:

Table 1.2 shows frequencies and percentage of respondents for each IT company under study.

Table 1.2

Respondents' Frequency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1. Advanced Informatics	1	20.0	20.0	20.0
	2. Analyse-IT Technologies	1	20.0	20.0	40.0
	3. B Factor Technologies (P) Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	60.0
	4. Binary Global Limited	1	20.0	20.0	80.0
	5. Class Notify Technologies	1	20.0	20.0	20.0
	6. Connect Info soft Technologies Pvt. Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	50.0
	7. Damco Solutions Pvt. Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	30.0
	8. E Web Solutions Net	1	20.0	20.0	20.0
	9. Enable Inc.	1	20.0	20.0	50.0

10. FutureSoft India Com	1	20.0	20.0	50.0
11. Info-edge Solutions	1	20.0	20.0	80.0
12. Learning Information Systems (I) Pvt. Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	40.0
13. IT Recruitment Services	1	20.0	20.0	60.0
14. G8 Net Pvt. Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	30.0
15. Flair Media	1	20.0	20.0	60.0
Total	15	300.0	300.0	345.0

Source: Primary Data, Author's Compilation

As shown in Table 1.2, frequency of each company out of 15 is equal to 1 and valid 20 percent responses received from each company in three groups. Although cumulative percentage was higher for most of the companies because total responses received were somewhat more than 20 percent taken for further analysis.

STATISTICS OF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT:

Frequencies:

Table 1.3 shows frequencies and percentage of respondents for each IT company under study for training and development.

Table 1.3

Training and Development Statistics

		Respondent Companies	Training and Development	Management Appraisal	Judgmental Process
N	Valid	15	5	15	15
	Missing	0	0	0	0
Mean			24.00	21.80	19.20
Std. Error of Mean			.775	.917	1.200
Median			25.00	21.00	19.00
Mode			25	20(a)	19
Std. Deviation			1.732	2.049	2.683
Variance			3.000	4.200	7.200
Skewness			-1.925	.441	-.999
Std. Error of Skewness			.913	.913	.913
Percentiles	25		22.50	20.00	17.00
	50		25.00	21.00	19.00
	75		25.00	24.00	21.50

(a) Multiple modes exist. The smallest value is shown. Source: Primary Data, Author's Compilation

As can be seen the statistics of Training and Development, Management Appraisal and Judgmental Process from Table 1.3, there exist significant difference between mean values of responses about these activities in the IT companies under study. Training and development has highest value 24.00 followed by management appraisal 21.80 and 19.20 of judgmental process. Median and mode values are also in similar trend as mean values for these activities.

Standard deviation was highest i.e., 2.683 for judgmental process followed by 2.049 for management appraisal and lowest 1.732 for training and development. Similarly, variance was highest i.e., 7.200 for judgmental process followed by 4.200 for management appraisal and lowest 3.000 for training and development.

On the other hand, skewness value was 0.441 (highest) for Management Appraisal followed by - 0.999 for Judgmental Process and lowest with negative value -1.925 for Training and Development although standard error of skewness was equal i.e., 0.913 for all three activities.

Frequency Table for Respondent Companies

Table 1.4 shows frequency of five IT companies for training and development activities.

Table 1.4
Frequency of Respondent Companies

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Advanced Informatics	1	20.0	20.0	20.0
	Analyse-IT Technologies	1	20.0	20.0	40.0
	B Factor Technologies (p) Ltd	1	20.0	20.0	60.0
	Binary Global Limited	1	20.0	20.0	80.0
	Class Notify Technologies	1	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, Author’s Compilation.

It is clear that frequency is equal to 1 for all these companies and each having 20 percent respondents contribution.

Training and Development

The following Table 1.5 showing valid responses for training and development.

Table 1.5
Frequency for Training and Development

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	21	1	20.0	20.0	20.0
	24	1	20.0	20.0	40.0
	25	3	60.0	60.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, Author’s Compilation.

There was one group of 21 respondents, one group of 24 and three groups of 25 respondents and as obvious from Table 1.5, each group has valid 20 percent response.

Management Appraisal

The following Table 1.6 showing valid responses for management appraisal.

Table 1.6
Frequency for Management Appraisal

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20	2	40.0	40.0	40.0
	21	1	20.0	20.0	60.0
	24	2	40.0	40.0	100.0
	Total	5	100.0	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, Author’s Compilation

There were two groups of 20 respondents each, one group of 21 respondents and other two groups of 24 respondents each as can be seen from Table 1.6, and each individual group has valid 20 percent response.

Conclusions:

Sustainability is an emerging phenomenon in HRM practice and research. As the world has entered the 21st century, companies found themselves in need to develop more sustainable business models, and the HR function has a key role to play in the process. This paper has attempted to make a contribution to both: sustainability and HRM literature. Firstly, it provided a short historical analysis of the emergence and different origins of understanding sustainability in HRM. Then, as a contribution to sustainability literature, research findings of nine highly sustainable corporations were presented and the areas of HR's greatest contribution and areas needing more HR contribution were indicated. The analysis of a small sample of the corporations suggests the existence of some relationship between the HR function's positioning in the firm and the degree of its contribution in areas of sustainability-related HR practices.

The challenge HR is now facing is to step up to this call and develop the necessary capabilities to help foster greater business and world sustainability.

Findings from Responses of Questionnaire:

- Most of the respondents were agreed that they were well aware about the qualification required to perform the job before being hired.
- Majority of the applicants sourced through effective methods of recruitment such as jobsites, social media, print media, referrals etc whereas a significant number was of those applicants at the same time who were came through directly or other sources.
- Exactly half of the applicants (50 percent) were agreed that formal tests being conducted for selection whereas 36 percent were disagreed and opined that formal test norms were not applied either partially or entirely.
- Majority of respondents were agreed that first preference has been given to qualified employees of the company for any vacancies fulfillment which is a good practice.
- Interviews structure changes remarkably for candidate to candidate and there is a lack of similarity between interviews taken for recruitment.
- Very low (only 5%) number of respondents was strongly agreed and a hugh number (more than 40%) of respondents were disagreed. It indicates that IT companies under study are not identifying the Training and Development needs on a timely basis.
- Flatter organizations and focus on agility will change HRD practices.
- HRD Transformation projects will accelerate in future.
- Global leadership and bench-strength will be a high priority.
- Globalization of HRD and talent practices will be a major focus.

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS:

- Organizations must have the capacity to relate those aptitudes and abilities to a part or a focal point of interest, for example, an occupation position, and task or initiative part.
- Talent administration forms must make an exhaustive profile of their ability. They should have the capacity to track significant ability related data about the majority of their kin -representatives, temporary workers, or hopefuls.
- The working society of the association ought to be enhanced and kept up to hold ability in long run.
- More confirmed preparing ought to be given to the workers to support their adequacy and effectiveness. It ought to be utilized as an instrument of inspiration.
- The association ought to distinguish the vital ability activity to pull in and hold the worker. They ought to know which ability administration components can have the best effect on the business and in this way give a superior premise to prioritization and usage.

- To make a refined ability administration environment, IT companies must:
 - a. Define an unmistakable vision for ability administration.
 - b. Develop a guide for innovation and procedure.
 - c. Integrate and improve forms.
 - d. Apply strong innovation to empower forms.

- The business procedure must be connected with the human asset system. It is vital to consider the varying attributes of individuals when setting an arrangement for an association to take after.

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